

Analyzing Factors Influencing Purchase Intention for Crevolene Products from Evolene Company: A Study on Brand, Packaging, Promotion, Price, and Quality

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ABSTRACT: The Indonesian market for dietary supplements, including products like creatine supplement, has seen significant growth due to the increasing focus on health and wellness. With a rise in fitness activities and a health-conscious population, there is a target market for such supplements. From the interview with the CEO of Evolene, it revealed a notable fluctuation in Crevolene sales since November 2022, raising concerns about revenue stability and sustainable growth. Understanding the contributing factors, such as changing consumer preferences, market dynamics, and pricing fluctuations, is crucial to develop effective marketing strategies. Preliminary findings suggest that Crevolene is gaining recognition among individuals who engage in regular workout routines, indicating a potential target market. By focusing marketing efforts on this segment and analyzing purchase intentions, Evolene can tailor strategies to increase sales and align with customer preferences. Further research is needed to refine market segmentation and develop precise targeting strategies. The purposes of this study are to identify the factors that influence Crevolene product from Evolene company sales and to increase sales of Crevolene product of Evolene Company. This study uses a quantitative research method with descriptive statistics. The sample for this research consists of 207 respondents taken by using non-probability sampling method. The questionnaire will employ a Likert scale with five levels, representing an interval scale. Questionnaire will be distributed online. The research tool used in this research is questionnaire. The data analysis methods used are validity test, reliability test, classic assumption test and hypothesis testing using SPSS software. Based on the research results showed that price, promotion and packaging have significant influence on purchase intention. Consumers before making a purchase, commonly check pricing among several brands or goods. A product's competitive pricing or superior value as compared to alternatives might influence consumers' buying intentions. A product may become more alluring when compared to more expensive choices thanks to price reductions or promotions, Promotions frequently include discounts, exclusive deals, or incentives, which give the buyer the impression that they are getting more for their money. Their opinion that they are receiving a good price or additional benefits may affect their decision to buy, also packaging that is attractive and well-designed may draw customers in, stand out on store shelves, and provide a good first impression.

KEYWORDS: Brand, Purchase Intention, Price, Quality, Promotion, Packaging

INTRODUCTION

The consumption of dietary supplements has experienced significant growth in Indonesia in recent years. With a growing focus on health and wellness, more Indonesians are turning to supplements to support their fitness goals and overall well-being. Based on Neurosensum data, Indonesian supplement consumption increased as much as 73% in the post pandemic era. The rising interest in fitness and health-consciousness has played a crucial role in driving the growth of the supplement market in Indonesia. A considerable portion of the population is actively engaged in physical activities, such as fitness training, bodybuilding and sports, creating a target market for products like Crevolene. With the combination of a growing population, rising GDP, and an increasing focus on health and wellness, the demand for dietary supplements, including creatine products like Crevolene, is on the rise in Indonesia. To capitalize on this favorable market environment, Evolene Company must identify and implement effective marketing strategies to position Crevolene as the preferred choice among fitness enthusiasts and athletes. This thesis aims to propose comprehensive marketing strategies for the Crevolene product from Evolene Company specifically tailored for the Indonesian market. The strategies will focus on improving brand visibility, effectively reaching the target audience, and stimulating consumer demand within the unique cultural and market landscape of Indonesia. By leveraging the population size and the correlation between rising GDP and consumer spending, Evolene Company can design marketing initiatives that resonate with Indonesian consumers and capitalize on their increasing

inclination toward health and wellness products. To develop these marketing strategies, a thorough examination of the current marketing landscape in Indonesia will be conducted. This analysis will include competitor research, consumer segmentation, and market trends to identify potential opportunities for Evolene Company to differentiate Crevolene from competitors and establish a strong market presence. The proposed strategies will encompass various channels, including digital marketing, influencer collaborations, strategic partnerships with local fitness communities, and targeted advertising campaigns tailored to Indonesian consumers, to maximize brand exposure and impact. The successful implementation of the proposed marketing strategies for Crevolene in Indonesia will not only drive increased sales for Evolene Company but also strengthen its brand equity and establish a sustainable competitive advantage in the Indonesian market. By capitalizing on Indonesia's growing population, rising GDP, and the increasing focus on health and wellness, Evolene Company can unlock new avenues for growth and solidify its position as a market leader in the creatine supplement segment within the country. This thesis aims to serve as a valuable resource for Evolene Company's marketing team, providing practical insights and recommendations to guide the successful marketing of Crevolene in Indonesia. By adopting the proposed strategies, Evolene Company can proactively respond to the unique market dynamics in Indonesia, capitalize on the correlation between rising GDP and consumer spending, and achieve long-term business growth within the Indonesian market. Through the implementation of these strategies, Crevolene can become the top choice for fitness enthusiasts and athletes in Indonesia, driving increased sales and establishing Evolene Company as a leader in the creatine supplement market within the country.

BUSINESS ISSUES

The interview with the CEO of Evolene indicate that since November 2022, there has been a notable fluctuation in Crevolene sales. This fluctuation in sales raises concerns for Evolene Company regarding revenue stability, market performance, and the ability to achieve sustainable growth. The fluctuating sales of Crevolene present a critical challenge for Evolene Company, impacting its financial performance and market position. Understanding the underlying factors contributing to these sales fluctuations is crucial for developing effective marketing strategies to stabilize sales and drive consistent growth. Several factors may contribute to the fluctuating sales of Crevolene, including changing consumer preferences, market dynamics, competitive pressures, pricing fluctuations, or fluctuations in promotional efforts. Analyzing these factors will provide insight into the root causes of sales fluctuations and help identify areas for improvement. Evolene sells their products through B2C. The channels that they are using are E-commerce, social media, offline store and gym. The interview result also stated that the sales of Crevolene products are fluctuating in every possible channel. They did a promotion by giving a discount to their product. Based on a preliminary study involving interviews with 12 individuals, the findings reveal that Crevolene is currently gaining recognition predominantly among individuals who engage in regular workout routines. 7 of the interviewee that known about the product working out at least once a week and the rest that didn't know about the product are individuals that not working out routinely. These individuals who workout routinely, emerge as a potential target market for Crevolene. The study suggests that the product has yet to achieve widespread awareness beyond this specific consumer segment. The insights gathered from the interviews provide valuable initial indications regarding the market positioning of Crevolene. By focusing marketing efforts on individuals who regularly participate in workout activities, Evolene Company can tailor its messaging and promotional strategies to reach this specific target audience. Recognizing this niche market's familiarity and potential interest in the benefits of creatine supplementation, Evolene Company can direct resources towards targeted marketing campaigns, engaging fitness influencers, and leveraging platforms that resonate with exercise enthusiasts. The preliminary study highlights the need for Evolene Company to focus its marketing efforts on individuals who regularly engage in workout routines, as they represent a receptive and potentially lucrative target market for Crevolene. Further research and analysis will be necessary to refine and validate these initial findings, allowing for more precise market segmentation and effective targeting strategies to be developed. From the symptoms that occurring, the author made a continue interview with the founder and CEO of Evolene, Mr. Christian Dicky and found that Evolene company did not analyzed the purchase intention of the product. Analyzing purchase intention is essential in addressing the business issue of fluctuating Crevolene sales mentioned earlier. By understanding customers' intentions and motivations to purchase Crevolene, the marketing strategies can be tailored to effectively target and influence their decision-making processes, ultimately increasing sales and driving consistent growth. Purchase intention informs the proposed analyzing marketing strategies by identifying target customer segments, optimizing product positioning, addressing barriers to purchase, and evaluating the effectiveness of marketing campaigns. By incorporating this analysis into the marketing strategy development process, Evolene Company can effectively align its efforts with customers' intentions, increase the likelihood of

converting intentions into sales, and ultimately achieve the objective of increasing Crevolene product sales. The root cause of the fluctuating sales of Crevolene can be attributed to Evolene Company's lack of awareness regarding the importance of marketing strategy and understanding product attributes to remain competitive. By recognizing the need for effective marketing strategies and conducting market research, Evolene Company can gain valuable insights into customer preferences, enhance their marketing efforts, and develop a competitive edge in the market.

METHODOLOGY

This study uses a quantitative research method, namely a research method based on the philosophy of positivism, used to examine certain populations or samples, data collection uses research instruments, data analysis is quantitative or statistical, with the aim of testing the hypotheses that have been set [1]. In this study, the authors used descriptive statistics. Descriptive statistics are statistics that are used to analyze data by describing or describing the data that has been collected as it is without intending to make general conclusions or generalizations [2]. This research is a type of survey research, namely research used by using a questionnaire as a research tool. The sample for this research consists of 207 respondents. Non-probability sampling is employed, where respondents are selected based on the authors' evaluations and convenience in collecting data rather than offering an equal chance to all individuals. The questionnaire will employ a Likert scale with five levels, representing an interval scale. The distribution of the questionnaire will be conducted online, making it an online survey. The list of questionnaire items is attached in Table 1. SPSS software will be used to quantitatively test the data and analyze it to determine the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. Validity test is a test used to measure the validity of a tool or instrument used to obtain data in a study. Reliability testing is a research method used to assess the consistency and stability of measurement tools or instruments [3].

Table 1. Variable and question for questionnaire (Author, 2023)

Variable	Question
Quality	1. Crevolene is a high quality product (QUALITY1) 2. Crevolene is a reliable product according to its benefits (QUALITY2) 3. Crevolene has guaranteed safety (QUALITY3) 4. the quality of Crevolene products competes with its competitors in the market (QUALITY4)
Brand	1. I noticed that there is a creatine product by the name Crevolene by Evolene (BRAND1) 2. Crevolene from Evolene is a trusted brand (BRAND2) 3. I will choose the Crevolene from Evolene brand over other similar brands in the market (BRAND3) 4. I can recognize Crevolene creatine from Evolene products well (BRAND4)
Price	1. The price of Crevolene is competitive with other creatine products on the market in my opinion (PRICE1) 2. The price of Crevolene is worth the value (PRICE2) 3. I am satisfied with the price offered by the Crevolene supplement (PRICE3) 4. The price of Crevolene is a reflection of the quality and reputation of the Evolene brand (PRICE4)
Promotion	1. The promotion of Crevolene supplements is interesting (PROMO1) 2. The Crevolene promotion makes this product stand out from the competition in the market (PROMO2) 3. Crevolene promotion is very clear and easy to understand (PROMO3) 4. The Crevolene promotion accurately represents the product and its benefits (PROMO4) 5. The Crevolene promotion adds value to the product (PROMO5)
Packaging	1. The Crevolene packaging is visually appealing (PACK1) 2. Crevolene packaging makes the product look high quality (PACK2) 3. Crevolene packaging provides precise information about the nutritional content (PACK4) 4. Crevolene packaging stands out compared to other similar products in the market (PACK5)
Purchase Intentions	1. I intend to buy Crevolene products in the near future (INT1) 2. I am sure about my decision to buy Crevolene because of the good quality of the product (INT2) 3. I decided to buy Crevolene based on other people's experiences (INT3) 4. I will never/never be disappointed buying Crevolene because of the good quality of the product (INT4) 5. I bought Crevolene because it's easy to find and get (INT5)

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Statistical Analysis

1) Validity Test

Validity test is a test used to measure the validity of a tool or instrument used to obtain data in a study. A questionnaire is declared valid if the questions on the questionnaire are able to reveal something to be measured for the questionnaire [4]. The validity of the data is established through Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO), and factor loading analysis. The data can be considered as valid when they have KMO value more than 0,5, and factor loading more than 0,6. Table 2 illustrate the result.

Table 2. Validity test (SPSS 25, 2023)

Indicators	Loading Factor	KMO
QUALITY1	0,735	0,731
QUALITY2	0,773	
QUALITY3	0,7	
QUALITY4	0,658	
BRAND1	0,884	0,832
BRAND2	0,863	
BRAND3	0,902	
BRAND4	0,878	
PRICE1	0,756	0,811
PRICE2	0,852	
PRICE3	0,841	
PRICE4	0,895	
PROMO1	0,616	0,753
PROMO2	0,704	
PROMO3	0,806	
PROMO4	0,777	
PROMO5	0,668	
PACK1	0,816	0,808
PACK2	0,816	
PACK3	0,812	
PACK4	0,837	
INT1	0,746	0,684
INT2	0,786	
INT3	0,694	
INT4	0,618	

Based on above result (Table 2), all indicators in each variable are met the requirement.

2) Reliability Test

The reliability of the data is established by looking the value of Cronbach’s alpha. The data can be concluded as reliable when the Cronbach’s alpha value is more than 0,6. Table 3 interpret the result.

Table 3. Reliability test (SPSS 25, 2023)

Indicator	Cronbach Alpha
QUALITY	0,669
BRAND	0,904
PRICE	0,858
PROMO	0,756
PACK	0,837
INT	0,670

The SPSS output shows that all variables are met the requirement which have Cronbach’s Alpha value more than 0,6. It can be concluded that all variables are reliable.

B. Classic Assumption Test

1) Normality Test

Normality test is used to test regression model whether the dependent variable and independent variable have normal distribution or not. Normality data is tested using residual data from each model and a method called One Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov. If the p-value is more than 0.05, it means the residual data is normally distributed.

Table 4. Normality test (SPSS 25, 2023)

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Unstandardized Residual
N		207
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	0,0000000
	Std. Deviation	1,84276709
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	0,055
	Positive	0,055
	Negative	-0,041
Test Statistic		0,055
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		,200 ^{c,d}

- a. Test distribution is Normal.
- b. Calculated from data.
- c. Lilliefors Significance Correction.
- d. This is a lower bound of the true significance.

As we can see in the output of Table 4, shows that the unstandardized residual is above 0.05 or 0,200, means that the model is normally distributed.

2) Homogeneity Test

Homogeneity Test or Heteroscedasticity test is used to test inequality equation model residual variance from one observation to another observation. To test whether the model’s heteroscedasticity or not, can be measured by using scatter plot graph between prediction of the dependent variable value (ZPRED) and the residual (SRESID).

Based on the output, the residual data is spread randomly and didn’t create any specific pattern. It means there is no heteroscedasticity in all research model.

C. Hypothesis Testing

1) R-Square Test (Coefficient of Determination)

R-squared, also known as the coefficient of determination, is a statistical measure that indicates the proportion of the variance in the dependent variable that can be explained by the independent variables in a regression model.

Table 5. R-square test (coefficient of determination) (SPSS 25, 2023)

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	,707 ^a	0,499	0,487	1,866	1,837

a. Predictors: (Constant), PACK, PROMO, PRICE, BRAND, QUALITY

b. Dependent Variable: INT

According to the results, the explanatory power show by R-square value 0.499 which have moderate power and also could be concluded that 49,9% of INT can be explained by PACK, PROMO, PRICE, BRAND and QUALITY.

2) F-Statistic Test

The F-test is a statistical test used to compare the variances of two or more groups or populations. It helps determine if there are significant differences in the means of the groups being compared. If the calculated F-value is greater than the critical value obtained from the F-distribution table or if the p-value associated with the F-value is smaller than a predetermined significance level (e.g., $\alpha = 0.05$), then it can be concluded that there are significant differences among the group means.

Table 6. F-test (SPSS 25, 2023)

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	697,578	5	139,516	40,088	,000 ^b
	Residual	699,533	201	3,480		
	Total	1397,111	206			

a. Dependent Variable: INT

b. Predictors: (Constant), PACK, PROMO, PRICE, BRAND, QUALITY

The F-statistic also shows a significant value (Sig < 0,05) means there are simultaneous effect between PACK, PROMO, PRICE, BRAND, QUALITY, and INT.

3) t-Statistic Test

Hypothesis testing is used to rule out the null hypothesis (Ho), allowing the alternative hypothesis (Ha) to be considered. It's possible to do so by examining the importance of each relationship's worth. As for fault tolerance limits (α) used is 5%. If the p-value is below 0,05 (< 0,05), there are significant effects between independent variables against the dependent variable. As summary table to hypothesis testing in accordance with the objectives of this research can be seen in Table 7.

Table 7. t-test (SPSS 25, 2023)

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	4,885	1,481		3,298	0,001
	QUALITY	0,145	0,091	0,121	1,602	0,111
	BRAND	0,051	0,045	0,083	1,140	0,256
	PRICE	0,227	0,053	0,302	4,290	0,000
	PROMO	0,333	0,074	0,338	4,486	0,000
	PACK	0,140	0,062	0,114	2,262	0,025

a. Dependent Variable: INT

Table 7 show that the t-value of QUALITY is 1,602, with the level of significance = 0,111 which is bigger than 0,05 ($p > 0,05$) and $\beta = 0,145$; means H1 is rejected. This shows that there is no influence of quality towards purchase intention. The beta value positive, it means that quality provide positive influence towards purchase intention. While quality typically has a significant impact on purchase intention, it is possible that other factors such as price, promotion, convenience, or personal preferences may outweigh the influence of quality in certain situations. The perceived importance of quality can vary among different consumer segments and product categories especially for fitness supplement brands.

Obtained result shows the t-value of BRAND is 1,140, with the level of significance = 0,256 which is bigger than 0,05 ($p > 0,05$) and $\beta = 0,051$; means H2 is rejected. This shows that there is no influence of brand towards purchase intention. The beta value positive, it means that brand provide positive influence towards purchase intention. Brand can significantly affect purchase intention due to several reasons like brand reputation, brand awareness, brand loyalty, brand differentiation and many more. However, it is also possible for a brand to have an insignificant effect on purchase intention in certain situations. Factors such as product attributes, pricing, promotions, or other external influences may outweigh the impact of brand alone.

The result shows the t-value of PRICE is 4,290, with the level of significance = 0,000 which is smaller than 0,05 ($p < 0,05$) and $\beta = 0,227$; means H3 is accepted. This shows that there is the influence of price towards purchase intention. The beta value positive, it means that price provide positive influence towards purchase intention. Consumers frequently compare prices across different brands or products before making a purchase decision. If a product is competitively priced or offers better value compared to alternatives, it can sway purchase intention in its favor. Price discounts or promotions can make a product more appealing in comparison to higher-priced options.

Similarly, the result shows the t-value of PROMO is 4,486, with the level of significance = 0,000 which is smaller than 0,05 ($p < 0,05$) and $\beta = 0,333$; means H4 is accepted. This shows that there is the influence of promotion towards purchase intention. The beta value positive, it means that promotion provide positive influence towards purchase intention. This is reasonable since promotions often involve discounts, special offers, or incentives, which create a perception of greater value for the consumer. This perception of getting a good deal or extra benefits can positively influence their purchase intention.

Furthermore, the results demonstrate that the t-value PACK is 2,262, with the level of significance = 0,025 which is smaller than 0,05 ($p < 0,05$) and $\beta = 0,140$; means H5 is accepted. This shows that there is the influence of packaging towards purchase intention. The beta value positive, it means that packaging provides positive influence towards purchase intention. Packaging plays a vital role in attracting consumers' attention. Well-designed and visually appealing packaging can capture consumers' interest, stand out on store shelves, and create a positive first impression. Aesthetically pleasing packaging can evoke positive emotions and make consumers more inclined to consider purchasing the product. Evolene offering various

packaging that also have various flavor (Hazelnut, Mocha, Grape, etc) with different color may be eye catching for their potential customer and consider to buy this product whenever they want to build their muscle or going to gym.

CONCLUSION

Eventhough Evolene has been established since 2020 and being awarded as a Top Brand Award in 2023, there are a few aspects that need to be improved in order to maintain the products purchase intention and sustainability.

In order to increase the intention to purchase of Evolene products, Evolene need to focus to maximize the three factors that are influencing the purchase intention; price, promotion and packaging.

RECOMMENDATIONS

A. *For Theoretical Implication*

The findings of this research enrich consumer behavior theory by emphasizing the significance of price, promotion, and packaging as influential factors in shaping purchase intentions, expanding our understanding of consumer decision-making processes. Additionally, the thesis enhances marketing theory by highlighting how marketers can strategically leverage these variables to shape consumer perceptions and behaviors, providing valuable insights for effective marketing strategies. The research also aligns with Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) theory, underscoring the synergistic effects of price, promotion, and packaging and emphasizing the importance of a cohesive marketing approach in influencing consumer responses. By bridging consumer psychology theories and marketing practices, the thesis investigates the underlying psychological processes that drive consumer decision-making, leading to a deeper understanding of the cognitive and emotional mechanisms involved. The practical implications of this research are valuable for marketing practitioners, as evidence-based recommendations for pricing strategies, promotional activities, and packaging designs are provided, enabling strategic marketing planning in the supplement industry.

B. *For Evolene Management*

Our research shows that price, promotion and packaging plays a crucial role in consumers' purchase intention for Crevolene products. To leverage this finding, we recommend that Evolene adopt a competitive pricing strategy. Conduct a thorough analysis of the market to determine the average price range for similar products. By offering products at a competitive price point, Evolene can attract price-sensitive customers and gain a competitive edge. Additionally, consider implementing promotional pricing strategies, such as limited-time discounts or bundle offers, to further stimulate purchase intentions. Promotion is another significant factor influencing purchase intention in the supplement market. Evolene should invest in targeted promotional activities to create awareness and generate interest in its products. Develop a comprehensive marketing plan that includes both online and offline channels. Utilize social media platforms, influencer collaborations, and digital marketing campaigns to reach a wider audience. Consider partnering with fitness influencers or health professionals who can endorse your products, as their recommendations can significantly impact purchase intention. Additionally, explore traditional marketing channels such as print advertisements in fitness magazines or health-related events to increase brand visibility. Our research highlights the importance of packaging in influencing consumers' purchase intention. Evolene should invest in attractive and informative packaging designs that appeal to its target market. Consider incorporating elements such as vibrant colors, clear product descriptions, and visually appealing graphics that convey the product's benefits. Additionally, emphasize any unique features or ingredients that differentiate Evolene's products from competitors. A well-designed package can catch consumers' attention, create a positive first impression, and ultimately increase purchase intention.

C. *For Future Research*

Future research should investigate specific packaging elements that have the most significant impact on purchase intention, such as color, design, typography, or labeling. Since in this study, we did not mention any specific part of design / color that consumer prefer to choose when purchasing supplement products. Analyze the effectiveness of different promotional strategies, such as discounts, limited-time offers, loyalty programs, or influencer partnerships, on purchase intention of each Evolene products. Even though brand and quality on this research are insignificant affecting purchase intention, the future researcher should conduct studies to understand the specific attributes or dimensions of brand and quality that are relevant to consumers in the fitness supplement industry. Last, due to the competition in fitness supplements in Indonesia are quite high we recommending

to do comparative research to understand how Evolene's packaging, promotions, and pricing strategies fare against competitors in terms of their impact on purchase intention.

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